

Working instructions for publishing coded objects

Scope	<p>The Knowledge Junction is a curated, open repository for the exchange of evidence and supporting materials used in food and feed safety risk assessments, with the goal of improving transparency, reproducibility and evidence reuse. Submissions of evidence (reports, datasets, images, videos, laboratory outputs, etc.) and supporting materials (software, tools, models, code, protocols, appraisal schemes, FAQs etc.) are welcome from any registered user of Zenodo. Each submission is assigned a digital object identifier (DOI), requires metadata acknowledging authors and contributors and has a license specifying the conditions of use. In this way the reuse of any object deposited can be tracked the provider. The content of this repository can be used by EFSA's panels and working groups and any other interested parties when preparing for new risk assessments. Supporting materials generated during risk assessment are also available on this platform.</p> <p>The document describes the metadata requirements for publishing coded objects in Knowledge Junction. Working instructions for other digital object types are in preparation</p>
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Relevant standards, procedures, legislation and documents	<p>Dublin Core Metadata Element Set ISO Standard 15836:2009 Global Agricultural Concept Scheme Creative commons licenses EFSA authorship principles The EU Food Safety Almanac EFSA Strategy 2020 Knowledge Junction</p>
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Abbreviations and definitions

Author	An entity primarily responsible for making the resource
Curator	Content specialist or project manager charged with contributing to and maintaining the repository collection
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
Digital Object	Electronic file or files

Global Agricultural Concept Scheme	<p>The Global Agricultural Concept Scheme (GACS) is a hub for concepts related to agriculture, in multiple languages, for use in Linked Data. It comprises a core set of terms from the thesauri of the Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (FAO), CAB International (CABI), and the National Agricultural Library of the USA (NAL)</p>
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Objects suitable for submission to the repository

- Objects which already have a DOI should **not** be published in the repository
- Objects which are subject to copy right restrictions should **not** be published in the repository
- All other evidence and supporting materials of relevant for food and feed safety will be accepted if the metadata provided is completed according to the instructions below

Prepare the metadata

Publication Type	Software	Required
Digital Object Identifier	Zenodo will generate a unique DOI for each item submitted	
Publication Date	The day of submission is the default	Required
Title	Provide a short name for the digital object submitted	Required
Authors	<p>As a minimum provide the name of the organisation/affiliation which created the digital object.</p> <p>However since the repository is designed to foster collaboration the names of the authors are preferred as this allows people who download objects to contact the author</p> <p>Names should be reported as Surname, Forename</p> <p>Affiliation: The EU Food Safety Almanac can be used as a source for the confirmation organisation names.</p> <p>EFSA authorship principles are recommended</p>	Required
Description	Provide a description of the coded object considering the purpose, scope, input and output parameters	Required

Keywords	Enter keywords that will help users of the repository to retrieve objects that are relevant for their area of research. Recommended terms for coded objects are provided below.	Required
Additional notes	Indicate the format for the submitted model For example - The model is implemented in The Microsoft Excel add-in software @Risk version 6.2.0 (Palisade Corporation).	
Access Right	Open Access	Required
License	<p>Recommended options for licensing are:</p> <p>Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Share — copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format Adapt — remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially Attribution — You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.</p> <p>Creative Commons Attribution No Derivatives (Used by the EFSA Journal) Share — copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format for any purpose, even commercially. Attribution — You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use. NoDerivatives — If you remix, transform, or build upon the material, you may not distribute the modified material.</p> <p>Other licensing options can be selected for example</p> <p>Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives Share — copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format The licensor cannot revoke these freedoms as long as you follow the license terms. Attribution — You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.</p>	Required

	<p>NonCommercial — You may not use the material for commercial purposes.</p> <p>NoDerivatives — If you remix, transform, or build upon the material, you may not distribute the modified material.</p> <p>No additional restrictions — You may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits.</p>	
Communities	Knowledge Junction	Required
Related identifiers	<p>Related links allows users to directly access relevant documentation describing the digital object.</p> <p>Any EFSA output incorporating, citing or based on the digital object must be linked using the DOI from the EFSA journal</p> <p>Any EFSA supporting publication incorporating, citing or based on the digital object must be linked using the DOI from the EFSA journal</p> <p>Other publications with either a DOI or ISSN that cite or are cited by the digital object can also be linked via Related identifiers.</p> <p>Where different versions of the same digital object exist within the repository, the Zenodo DOI should be used as the Related identifier to link these objects</p>	
Contributors	<p>Contributors are the people listed in the acknowledgements</p> <p>The process used for Authors should also be applied to contributors</p>	
References	<p>Any references cited in the Description should be included here.</p> <p>Additional references may be included at the discretion of the submitter</p> <p>However EFSA outputs and supporting publications should be linked using the Related identifiers rather than cited as references unless no DOI or ISSN exists</p>	
Subjects	<p>Each item must be classified using suitable terms selected from the Global Agricultural Concept Scheme</p> <p>This requires the term and the link to the Global</p>	

	<p>Agricultural Concept Scheme URI to be entered for each subject.</p> <p>A list of recommended terms for coded objects is provided below.</p>		
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Confirm metadata and publication rights

If the submitter is preparing coded objects for an organization (e.g. EFSA focal points) contact the author of the object to confirm the metadata and inform them of the planned publication in an open repository

Upload digital object in Knowledge Junction

To upload an object you must be a registered user of Zenodo. If you have an ORCID this can be used as your login credentials.
 Enter the Knowledge Junction community <https://zenodo.org/communities/efsa-kj>
 Use the upload function to publish the digital object with the prepared metadata.
 The community curator will review the metadata before acceptance into the community.

Recommended terminology for coded objects (note terms without a hyperlink can only be reported as keywords)

multi-compartment model: describes the way materials or energies are transmitted among the compartments of a system. Each compartment is assumed to be a homogeneous entity within which the entities being modelled are equivalent.

linear models: A model is linear when each term is either a constant or the product of a parameter and a predictor variable. A linear equation is constructed by adding the results for each term.

nonlinear models: not linear

neural networks: model designed to simulate the behavior of biological neural networks, as in pattern recognition, language processing, and problem solving, with the goal of self-directed information processing

network model: a mathematical model where the data is represented as a network of lines and nodes

empirical model: model based on investigations, observations, experiments, or experience, as opposed to theoretical knowledge based on logical or mathematical assumptions

	<p><u>mechanistic models:</u> a hypothesized relationship between the variables in the data set where the nature of the relationship is specified in terms of the biological processes that are thought to have given rise to the data</p> <p><u>statistical models:</u> Statistical formulations or analyses which, when applied to data and found to fit the data, are then used to verify the assumptions and parameters used in the analysis</p> <p>agent based models: agent based modeling can be defined as an essentially decentralized, individual-centric (as opposed to system level) approach to model design. Agents can be people, companies, vehicles, cities, animals, ships, products, plants, etc.,</p> <p>graphical models: define general message-passing algorithms that implement probabilistic inference efficiently</p> <p><u>simulation models:</u> A mathematical representation of the essential characteristics of a real-world system or situation, which can be used to predict future behavior under a variety of different conditions.</p> <p>hierarchical models: models in which the parameters of prior distributions are estimated from data rather than using subjective information. Hierarchical models are central to modern Bayesian statistics and allow an objective approach to inference.</p> <p><u>calculation:</u> performs basic arithmetic operations or more complex mathematical operations</p> <p><u>simulation:</u> the act of imitating the behavior of some situation or some process by means of something suitably analogous (e.g. Monte Carlo method)</p> <p><u>analytical methods:</u> solution directly solved from observed data</p> <p>numerical methods: is a complete and unambiguous set of procedures for the solution of a problem, together with computable error estimates (see error analysis).</p> <p><u>stochastic models:</u> A mathematical model involving random variable(s) in order to estimate probability distributions of potential outcomes.</p> <p>deterministic models: a deterministic system is a system in which no randomness is involved in the development of future states of the system. A deterministic model will thus always produce the same output from a given starting condition or initial state</p>
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<p><u>time</u>: model includes a temporal component</p> <p><u>spatial distribution</u>: model includes a spatial component</p> <p><u>uncertainty analysis</u>: a detailed examination of the systematic and random errors of a measurement or estimate; an analytical process to provide information regarding the uncertainty.</p> <p>sensitivity analysis = a technique used to determine how different values of an independent variable impact a particular dependent variable under a given set of assumptions</p> <p><u>model validation</u>: the process of determining the degree to which a model is an accurate representation of the real world from the perspective of the intended uses of the model</p> <p><u>population</u>: a group of individuals defined by a particular set of characteristics, e.g., organisms of a particular species living in a given region or area.</p> <p><u>groups</u>: A number of individual items or people brought together.</p> <p>individual: being an individual or existing as an indivisible whole</p> <p><u>forecasting</u>: the prediction or projection of the nature of future problems or existing conditions based upon the extrapolation or interpretation of existing scientific data or by the application of scientific methodology</p> <p><u>decision support systems</u>: a computer-based system that enables management to interrogate the computer system on an ad hoc basis for various kinds of information on the organization and to predict the effect of potential decisions beforehand</p> <p><u>exposure assessment</u>: the determination or estimation (qualitative or quantitative) of the magnitude, frequency, duration and route of exposure of a population.</p> <p>Sample size determination: it is the act to determine the sample size required to answer a specific research question</p> <p>maximum likelihood method: is a method of estimating the parameters of a statistical model given observations, by finding the parameter values that maximize the likelihood of making the observations given the parameters</p> <p>Approximate Bayesian Computation = data generated by simulation are then reduced to summary statistics, and the sampled parameters are</p>
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	<p>accepted or rejected on the basis of the distance between the simulated and the observed summary statistics</p> <p>Markov Chain Monte Carlo: an iterative Bayesian statistical technique that generates samples from the posterior distribution. Well-designed MCMC algorithms converge to the posterior distribution, which is independent of the starting position. Including variants such as particle MCMC</p>
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Document history

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Prepared by	Jane Richardson
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